

Proposal for a networking initiative to Coordinate Scientific Diver Training in Europe through MARS and ESDP

By Jouni Leinikki, ESDP's Finnish delegate

Much of the world's scientific diving and scientific diver training takes place at marine research stations at the sea. The aim of training courses is to qualify scientists to safely perform their tasks by diving or to enable them to utilize new skills and techniques underwater.

The standards for European Scientific Diver and Advanced European Scientific Diver developed by ESDP for scientific diver training provide a common framework for the basic initial SD training across Europe. This makes it possible, where applicable, to arrange international training courses and have joint pools of participants and training providers. It also enables a network to coordinate training courses to avoid overlapping events. Some course announcements have already been disseminated through ESDP mailing list.

ESDP and MARS can join forces to create a system of European-wide SD training. Such cooperation would benefit scientists and students by increasing the opportunities to obtain SD training filling the ESD standard. European training courses for new techniques would also serve as workshops and generate new science, and new common practices can be introduced to scientific diving through the training courses. Cooperation between marine stations also adds to their interaction and promotes other collaborations.

MARS stations have variable capacities to provide diving equipment and other facilities, while ESDP has connections between the SD instructors in different countries. These need to be assessed, as well as financing sources to assist course participation.

ESDP will coordinate the approval of training courses, ensure a quality control, and spread the information together with MARS.

High impact factor articles supported by Scientific Diving.

The ESDP schedules to update its publication list demonstrating that scientific diving is a highly valuable, even essential, research technique permitting significant results published in highest ranked journals. In 2015, ESDP completed a list of articles, published in journals with impact factor > 5. Some 60 articles were listed (<http://ssd.imbe.fr/To-highlight-benefits-of>).

The panel calls the marine station staff to update the list for the period 2015-2019.

Even if the only criterion IF is actually quite poor, it is an indicator that strikes the mind of policy and decision makers. The goal is to make scientific diving seen as a needed technique at the place it deserves among the scientific techniques.

Please send complete references (including the DOI) to jean-pierre.feral@imbe.fr

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